

BOKU CORE FACILITY MASS SPECTROMETRY

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Analysis report

ESI-MS analysis

Aim

Peptide analysis

Samples

4 insolution samples

Analyses performed

LC-ESI-MS/MS analysis of peptides originates from protease cleavage

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Peptide analysis:

The sample was digested in-solution. The proteins were S-alkylated with iodoacetamide and digested with Trypsin (Promega).

The digested samples were loaded on a nanoEase C18 column (nanoEase M/Z HSS T3 Column, 100Å, 1.8 µm, 300 µm X 150 mm, Waters) using 0.1 % formic acid as the aqueous solvent. A gradient from 1% B (B: 80% Acetonitrile, 0.1% FA) to 40% B in 50 min was applied, followed by a 10 min gradient from 40% B to 95% B that facilitates elution of large peptides, at a flow rate of 6 µL/min. Detection was performed with an Orbitap MS (Exploris 480, Thermo) equipped with the standard H-ESI source in positive ion, DDA mode (= switching to MSMS mode for eluting peaks). MS-scans were recorded (range: 350-1200 Da) and the 20 highest peaks were selected for fragmentation. Instrument calibration was performed using Pierce FlexMix Calibration Solution (Thermo Scientific).

The analysis files analysed using PEAKS, which is suitable for performing MS/MS ion searches. The files were searched against a *E. coli* database, containing the sequence of the target protein.

Additionally, the files were analysed manually to identify potential Tyrosine linkages by FreeStyle 1.8 (Thermo Scientific).

Results:

In the manual search, interlinked peptides could be identified in the wt-dimer sample. In the following, the chromatograms and spectra of the linked peptides are shown. In the wt sample the links could be not identified (see chromatograms).

WT-dimer

RT: 0.00-40.00

WT

RT: 0.00-40.00

	(M neutral)	2+	3+	4+	5+
VMLVIDAAVTNVEDLSSLEEYLASLGR	2906.495				
LFALEPDLLPLFQYNCR	2108.076				
linked peptide	5012.555	2507.285	1671.859	1254.146	1003.518

PaulF_Y44F_wt_dimer #20966-21162 RT: 37.27-37.57 AV: 9 NL: 3.92E6
T: MS

		chargestate							
	(M neutral)	2	3	4	5	6	7		
LFALEPDLLPLFQYNCR	2108.076								
LSSFSTVGSLLYMLEK	1902.965								
linked peptide	4009.026	2005.52	1337.34	1003.26	9	4	802.8124	669.1782	573.7252

PaulF_Y44F_wt_dimer #20386-20701 RT: 36.39-36.86 AV: 14 NL: 5.12E5
T: MS

		chargestate					
	(M neutral)	2	3	4	5	6	7
LFALEPDLLPLFQYNCR	2108.076						
AAWSQLYGAVVQAMSR	1736.867						
linked peptide	3842.928	1922.47	1281.98	961.739			
		1	3	2	769.5928	641.4952	549.9969

PaulF_Y44F_wt_dimer #19841-20008 RT: 35.56-35.81 AV: 7 NL: 9.88E5
T: MS

In the automated search in each of the samples multiple proteins could be identified.
Detailed results of the samples are presented in the files protein.html.

-10lgP: Protein Score: a more significant match will have a higher -10lgP value (<https://www.biocinfor.com/dbscoring-tutorial/>)
Coverage: sequence coverage of the protein identified by MS/MS
Area: Summed peptide area of extracted ion chromatograms (MS1)
#Peptides: number of identified peptides
#Unique: number of identified unique peptides
#Spec: peptide spectrum matches